

TEACHING OF SPEAKING THROUGH NEW METHODS

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Abstract: The proficiency of speaking becomes one of the five skills that should be acquired by every child in this 21 century era (Seamolec on line course 2: 2006). Communicating and collaborating and language boundaries become a necessity in diverse and multinational communities. Mutually beneficial relationships are a central undercurrent to accomplishment in Business (Partnership for 21st century skills: 2008). This research is aimed to investigate the teacher's strategies, problems and solutions for teaching speaking to young learners. A case study design was used in this study, and the data were collected through observation, interview, and written document. The data from these three instruments were analyzed qualitatively. This research has found several strategies promoted by the lecturer when teaching speaking to young learners. In the classroom activities, the lecturer used several strategies such as, role play, watching videos, jazz chant, digital storytelling, games, and repetition. The teachers might face several barriers in the classroom such as reluctant students, missing pronunciation and lack of vocabularies. But he can overcome those barriers by using various techniques of teaching speaking to young learners, such as implementing media and designing the lesson using topical-based syllabus (Pinter, 2006).

Keywords: Teaching strategies, Speaking skill, EYL

INTRODUCTION

The mastery of speaking skills in English is a necessary for many second language and foreign language students (Richard, 2008). Therefore, learners often appraise their language learning on how much they think they have developed their skill in spoken language skill. Besides, the proficiency of speaking becomes one of the five skills that should be acquired by every child in this 21 century era which is called as a communication skill (Seamolec on line course 2, 2006). Further, communicating and collaborating and language boundaries become a necessity in diverse and multinational communities. Mutually beneficial relationships are a central undercurrent to accomplishment in Business (Partnership for 21st century skills: 2008). In preparing every child to have a good communication skill, teaching speaking

is a primary requirement to be taught not only for adult learners but also for young learners. As stated by Slattery and Willis (2001), cited in Hakim (2011), English is being provided into initial classroom, such as Kindergarten and Elementary school, so that the teachers are needed to teach it into young learners. Further, to make the children to be able to speak English in communication, teachers need to guide the students to acquire the vocabulary and structures (Richard, 2008). In line with (Richard, 2008), Harmer (2007a, p. 123) proposes three major reasons for getting students to speak and to acquire new vocabulary in the classroom: 1). Speaking activities provide rehearsal opportunities 2). Speaking tasks in which students try to use any or all of the languages they know provide feedback for both teachers and students. 3). the more students have opportunities to activate the various language elements they have stored in their brains, the more automatic their use of these elements to become. Meanwhile, teaching speaking to young learners may give some difficulties to the teacher especially in Indonesia, since the young learners also consider speaking as a great challenge since it requires them to speak and think at the same time (Pinter, 2000). Besides, young learners are not necessarily competent communicators even in their mother tongue, and it reveals an idea that teaching speaking in Indonesia must be developed in EFL context.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK. The Nature of Speaking Speaking is a complex cognitive process (Graham-Marr, 2004) and an active use of language to express meaning (Cameron, 2001). It requires the language users to speak fluently, to be able to pronounce phonemes correctly, to use appropriate stress and intonation patterns, and to speak in connected speech (Harmer, 2007). In line with Harmer (2007), Chaney (cited in Kayi, 2006) defines speaking as a process of building and sharing meaning and information through the use of verbal and non-verbal symbols in variety context. In EFL context, the language users are also urged to speak in different genres and situation, and they will have to be able to use a range of conversational and conversational repair strategies (Harmer, 2007a). Teaching Speaking The goal of teaching speaking is communicative efficiency. Learners should be able to make themselves understood, using their current proficiency to the fullest. They should try to avoid confusion in the message due to faulty pronunciation, grammar, or vocabulary, and to observe the social and cultural rules that apply in each communication situation. To this relation, it is worth voting to what Nunan (2003) believes, which particularly dealing with teaching speaking. In his perception, to teach speaking can be defined as to teach the students to:

- Produce the English speech sound and sound patterns
- Use words and sentences stress, intonation patterns, and the rhythm of the second language
- Select the appropriate words and sentences according to the proper social setting, audience, situation and subject matter
- Organize their thoughts in a meaningful and logical sequence
- Use language as a mean of expressing values and judgments
- Use the language quickly and confidently with few unnatural pauses, which is called as fluency. To help the students in developing communicative efficiency in speaking, teachers can use a balanced activities approach which combines language input, structured output, and communicative output (Richard, p.2008). First, Language input comes in the form of teacher talk, listening activities, reading passages, and the language in which the students hear and read outside the class. It gives learners the material they need to begin producing language themselves. Language input may be content oriented or form oriented. Second, structured output focuses on correct form. In structured output, students may have options for responses, but all of the options require them to use the specific form or structure that the teacher has just introduced. Structured output is designed to make learners comfortable producing specific language items recently introduced, sometimes in combination with previously learned items. Instructors often use structured output exercises as a transition between the presentation stage and the practice stage of a lesson plan. Textbook exercises also often make good structured output practice activities. Third, communicative output, the learners' main purpose is to complete a task, such as obtaining information, developing a travel plan, or creating a video. To complete the task, they may use the language that the instructor has just presented, but they also may draw on any other vocabulary, grammar, and communication strategies that they know. In communicative output activities, the criterion of success is whether the learner gets the message across. Accuracy is not a consideration unless the lack of it interferes with the message. Teacher Roles in Teaching Speaking Paul (2003, p. 77) lists several principles that teachers need to consider in preparing students to communicate in English:
 1. Introducing and practicing patterns in ways that feel meaningful to the children, such as in games, in situation where the children genuinely want to express themselves, and through personalization.
 2. Practicing new patterns in combination with the other patterns the children have learned, so the children can internalize them more easily.

3. Giving the children many opportunities to guess how to use the patterns flexibly in novel situation
4. Giving the children confidence to speak out in front of others by king independently with other children and the whole class.
5. Building the children's inner strength to deal with confusing and novel situations, by presenting them with puzzles to overcome and solve, and making sure they are finally successful. Focusing on the question forms of new patterns, so the children can ask about things they do not know. They can learn Who is it? before or at the same time as learning, It's a cat, and, What's she doing? before or at the same time as learning She's sleeping. In line with Paul (2003), Harmer (2007b) and Terry (2008) classify roles of teacher in teaching speaking, as follows:
 1. Prompter: The teachers provide the students with discrete suggestions, leave them to struggle by themselves, and give them chunks not words, without disrupting the discussion.
 2. Participant: The teachers participate in the discussion by introducing new information and by ensuring the continuation of students' engagement. The main point is the teacher should not monopolize the conversation.
 3. Feedback provider: The teachers can give some feedbacks by giving helpful and gentle correction and by telling the students about their performance. Besides that, they should avoid over-correction, since it might lead to students' reluctance to continue the dialogue.
 4. Assessor: The teachers can write down some written samples of languages produced by students, or memorize some of it, then tell it to their students.
 5. Observer: The teachers should observe the class speaking activity and find out what makes the activity breakdown.
 6. Resource: The teachers have to provide some tools to improve their students' oral competence.
 7. Organizer: The teachers manage the classroom to set the activities and get the students engaged. In one teaching activity, the teachers might play more than one roles in the classroom. They can be a prompter in the middle of speaking of activity then in the end of the class they will play a role as feedback provider.

CONCLUSION

This section provides the conclusion of the present research. These conclusions are directly appointed to research problems formulated earlier in the previous section, i.e. 1. What are the teacher's strategies in enhancing

young learners' speaking proficiency? 2). What are the barriers faced by the teacher in teaching speaking? 3). How does the teacher overcome the barriers? This research has found several strategies promoted by the lecturer when teaching speaking to young learners. In the classroom activities, the lecturer used several strategies such as, role play, watching videos, jazz chant, digital storytelling, games, and repetition. The teachers might face several barriers in the classroom such as reluctant students, missing pronunciation and lack of vocabularies. But he can overcome those barriers by using various techniques of teaching speaking to young learners, such as implementing media and designing the lesson using topical-based syllabus (Pinter, 2006).

RECOMENDATION

Teaching speaking sounds seems easier since there are plenty of interesting techniques that can be employed in the classroom. However, there are still other considerations about teaching it to young learners. The teachers still need to take multiple-intelligence into account, because the teacher should meet each student's need in the classroom. There were several numbers of problems when this research was conducted such as the limited time for conducting the research and the lack of resources.

References:

1. Anuradha, RV, Raman, G, & Hemamalini, HC. 2014. Methods of Teaching English. Hyderabad: Neelkamal Publications.
2. Jyotsna, M&Rao, SN. 2009. Methods of Teaching English. Guntur: Sri Nagarjuna Publishers.
3. Kumari, AV. 2014. Methods of Teaching English. Guntur: New Era Publications.
4. Rao, VK. 2012. Techniques of Teaching English. Hyderabad: Neelkamal Publications.
5. Suchdeva, MS. 2011. A New Approach to Teaching of English in India. Ludhiana: Tandon Publications

